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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The internet has become a crucial source of health information, surpassing traditional sources (Wang et al., 2012). However, online information carries the risk of being incomplete, inaccurate, or outdated. Relying on such information without medical guidance may lead individuals to make incorrect health decisions and may harm the doctor-patient relationship (Norr, Capron, & Schmidt, 2014). The phenomenon, where repetitive online searches for medical information result in increased health anxiety, is termed "cyberchondria" (Starcevic & Berle, 2013; Starcevic et al., 2020). This study aims to identify the factors influencing the level of cyberchondria, contributing to mitigating its negative effects on the healthcare system and managing health anxiety in individuals.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted with voluntary participants consecutively visited our department's facilities in a six-month-period and was approved by the Non-Interventional Ethical Committee of Aydın Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Medicine on the 27th of February 2024 (Protocol number 2024/38, Decision number 03). The survey consists of two sections. The first section includes a total of 44 questions assessing participants' sociodemographic characteristics, general health status, healthcare utilization, communication with their doctor, and perspectives on health-related publications. The second section included the Cyberchondria Severity Scale Short Form (CSS-12). The CSS-12 scoring range is between 12 and 60 points, with higher total scores indicating higher levels of cyberchondria (McElroy et al., 2019). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 25.0. Significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Results: The study included 323 individuals with a mean age of 39.8 ± 14.2 years (18-72). Of the participants, 59.8% were female. The mean total score of CSS-12 was found to be 27.3 ± 8.9 , with a minimum score of 12 and a maximum score of 52. A significant positive correlation was identified between the total CSS-12 score and both the average daily internet usage time ($p < 0.001$) and the daily time spent searching for health-related information online ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, a statistically significant difference was found between the CSS-12 total score and both researching symptoms online before and/or after consulting a doctor ($p < 0.001$) and feeling comfortable asking their doctor about health-related issues ($p = 0.029$).

Conclusion: The findings of this study indicate that the duration of online health information searches increases the level of cyberchondria. Additionally, individuals who have a positive communication with their physicians exhibit lower levels of cyberchondria and this shows the importance of the doctor-patient relationship in this process. To mitigate the negative effects of cyberchondria, individuals should be encouraged to rely on credible health sources.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Cyberchondria, health anxiety, online health information

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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